

**pH and salinity evolution of Europa's brines . Raman spectroscopy
study of fractional precipitation at 1 and 300 bar**

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pH and salinity variation of Europa's brines

Abstract

Several evidences indicate the existence of salty liquid water below the icy surface of Europa satellite. Depending on the chemical composition of the original interior brines, minerals to precipitate will be different as well as the resulting physico-chemical parameters of the evolving solutions such as pH and salinity. These parameters are determinants to study the possible habitability of the satellite. In this work, experiments of fractional precipitation by cooling of several brines with different chemical composition (acid, alkaline and neutral) have been performed at 1 and 300 bar. The gradual decrease in temperature leads the mineral precipitation process, with consequently changes in salinity and pH values. Raman spectroscopy has been used to analyze quantitatively the variation of the salts concentration in the aqueous solutions during the experiments. The obtained laboratory data explain how cryomagma differentiation can occur in Europa. These endogenous processes of differentiation require planetary energy, which seems to have been plentiful during Europa geological history. Ultimately, the dissipation of part of that energy is translated to a higher complexity of the cryo-petrology in Europa crust. From the results, we conclude that fractional differentiation processes of briny cryomagmas produces several igneous salty mineral suites on icy moons.

- **Keywords:** *Europa; Salts; Chemical evolution; Raman spectroscopy; Volcanism.*

1. INTRODUCTION

From spectral signatures in the infrared it is well known that Europa satellite surface is mainly composed by water ice (Pilcher et al., 1972; Fink et al., 1973; McCord et al., 1999; Showman and Malhotra, 1999; Clark, 2003; Carlson et al., 2005; Shirley et al., 2010). Water is also in its interior, as ice I solid phase in the crust, and probably also as liquid (Anderson et al., 1998; Carr et al., 1998; Kattenhorn, 2002). The presence of a salty global ocean or local liquid reservoirs below or within the icy shell of the Jovian satellite respectively was proposed since several evidences were observed, such as: a) a self-induced magnetic field which may be caused at Europa by the flow of electrolytic salts through a liquid water ocean (Kivelson et al., 2000, Khurana et al. 1998, 2002); b) the morphology and topography of the chaotic terrains of the surface that suggest they may have been formed by resurfacing associated to rising liquid water located below the icy crust (Greenberg et al., 1999; Schimdt et al., 2011); and c) the non-water ice materials around Europa lineaments, which may have an endogenic origin (McCord et al., 1998; Dalton et al., 2005). Reflectance spectra of these materials show distorted and asymmetric water absorption bands at 1 and 2.5 μm , similar to those given by magnesium and sodium sulfates at high hydration state or hydrated sulfuric acid (Carlson et al., 1999). Since no proposed spectra of a single compound fits exactly with the spectra of these non-water ice materials, it is postulated that a mixture of them may be present. Optical signatures observed depend on the ion solvation, which is affected by the temperature of the ice. Orlando et al. (2005) carried out flash frozen experiments of sulfuric acid and some salt mixtures, obtaining spectra with a good correlation with NIMS data.

Several interpretations exist about the hydrate signature observed around the lineaments and the disrupted terrains. McCord et al. (2010) postulated that materials located at the center of these features have higher signal, and consequently are younger than those which are at the sides, since the last ones have water frost coverage. This observation can be understood as a succession of cryomagmas, composed by water, salts and volatiles, emerging into the crust like in terrestrial oceanic ridges (Rundquist and Sobolev, 2002). Nevertheless, theoretical models performed by Zolotov and Shock (2001) indicate that hydrated salts are more stable than water ice at Europa surface conditions; however, after brine evolution, salts arriving the surface will suffer a dehydration process. Some authors mention that a possible redeposition of sputtered water molecules can occur.

There are few models that consider compositional aspects during the evolution of Europa due to the scarce mineral and geochemical data available (Kargel, 1991; McCord et al., 1998, 1999). However, it may be assumed that during the thermal evolution of the icy satellites, if they have enough energy, cryomagmas can be produced in multi-component systems then evolve and rise to the surface in the same way as in terrestrial planets. When a cryomagma evolves, either during ascent or in a stabilized magmatic chamber or ocean level, the liquid solution can change its composition due to several processes, as happens with the primitive magmas on the Earth (Bowen, 1922; Turner and Campbell, 1986). The slow decrease in temperature promotes crystal fractionation since a gradual precipitation of various minerals occurs. Furthermore, the higher temperature of the cryomagmas with respect to the icy crust can eventually melt part of the crust, and an assimilation process would also take place. If during the evolution to the surface the cryomagmatic fluid contacts with other liquids with different chemical composition, they would even mix. However, buoyancy of

cryomagmas is necessary to be able to rise. Their lower density may occur if the icy shell is not formed by pure water ice or the cryomagma has dissolved volatiles such as CO₂. The endogenic hydrated materials on the surface would be interpreted as the last state occurred of the evolution of an inner cryomagma.

Neutral, acid and alkaline liquid aqueous solutions were proposed to exist in Europa interior (Kargel, 1991; Kargel et al., 2000; Marion, 2001; Marion, 2002; Marion et al., 2005) from the interaction of the rock and water systems. As mentioned before, the evolution of these brines to the surface may result in the non-water ice materials observed. Neutral brine, enriched mainly in magnesium sulfate (Kargel, 1991), would be the leachate at low temperature of a chondritic material, which has been proposed to be the original rock fraction of the satellite. In the case of the acid brine, it would come from the high temperature devolatilization and venting of sulfur dioxide from hydrothermal systems into the ocean (Kargel et al., 2001), which finally result in the enrichment of sulfuric acid. Pasek and Greenberg (2012) have proposed another hypothesis about the origin of sulfuric acid; which advocate that the oxidants formed at the surface migrate to the ocean, where they react with sulfides forming the acid. Natron (Na₂CO₃·10H₂O) is one of the candidates that can be present in the dark areas of Europa. These carbonates could be formed if CO₂ is vented in the aqueous reservoirs. Then, CO₂ reacts with H₂O forming carbonic acid (H₂CO₃). At pH above 8, the acid is dissociated in bicarbonate (HCO₃⁻) and carbonate (CO₃²⁻) anions and their reaction with the cations presents in the solution will be favourable (Langmuir, 1971; Millero and Roy, 1997).

In this work, we performed experiments of fractional precipitation of four different brines. The compositions, selected from the previous theoretical studies cited, are the following: a) Neutral brine: MgSO₄-Na₂SO₄-H₂O, b) Alkaline brine: Na₂SO₄-

Na₂CO₃-H₂O, c) Acid brine from the ternary system: MgSO₄-H₂SO₄-H₂O and d) Acid brine from the quaternary system: MgSO₄-Na₂SO₄-H₂SO₄-H₂O. They were studied at 1 and 300 bar, simulating the process at two differentiated depths from the surface. Assuming a crust of 20 km composed essentially by water ice, at 1 bar the aqueous systems would be at a depth less than 100 m, while a pressure up to 300 bar would correspond with a depth of about 25 km (Marion et al. 2005). Raman spectroscopy has been used to analyze “in situ” the concentration variation of the compounds along the cooling, since it allows a fast analysis without altering the sample and identifies quantitatively all the compounds of the system.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Reagents used to prepare the aqueous solutions for the experiments and calibrations were MgSO₄ · 7H₂O (≥ 99.5% purity, Sigma-Aldrich, US), Na₂SO₄ (≥ 99.0% purity, Sigma-Aldrich, US), Na₂CO₃ · 10H₂O (≥ 99.0% purity, Sigma-Aldrich, US), H₂SO₄ (95%, VWR, US) and Milli-Q water, with TOC lower than 5-10 ppb and resistivity higher than 18 MΩ cm. Initial molality concentration (m) of the supersaturated solutions selected were taken from the Marion (2001, 2002) and Marion et al. (2005) theoretical studies in order to be able to compare the results: a) Neutral brine: 1.63 m Na₂SO₄, 2.93 m MgSO₄; b) Alkaline brine: 4.50 m Na₂CO₃, 0.70 m Na₂SO₄; c) Acid brine from the ternary system: 3.82 m MgSO₄, 0.26 m H₂SO₄ and d) Acid brine from the quaternary system: 2.87 m MgSO₄, 0.81 m Na₂SO₄, 0.26 m H₂SO₄. Solutions have been prepared heating and stirring the solutions about 323 K to the complete dissolution of the salts.

Cooling has been made until the complete solidification of the brines (the eutectic). Thermostatization has been performed with a cooling bath, whose working temperature range is from 233 K to 323 K (TE-8D, Techne, UK), using ethanol 96% as coolant. To perform the experiments at 1 bar, each aqueous solution has been put in a 50 mL round-bottom flask, sealed with a septum. A thermocouple type T (HiP, US) with an accuracy of 0.02 K, was inserted in the flask to measure the temperature of the solution “in situ”. Then, the flask was immersed in the cooling bath.

For making the experiments at 300 bar, a high pressure cell has been used. A sketch of the equipment is shown in Fig. 1. The cell is made of stainless steel 304 and it has a hollow cylinder form, whose dimensions are 148 mm (length) x 50 mm (external diameter) x 24 mm (internal diameter). Two screw caps close it at the ends. One cap has a semi-conical sapphire window, sealed with Teflon® PTFE, of 8.60 mm length with base diameters of 9.35 and 5.05 mm respectively. The window allows the in situ analysis with an iHR550 Raman Spectrometer (Horiba YobinYvon, France). The other cap is connected to a hydraulic compressor (Ruska 7615, Ovredal, Spain), through a stainless steel tube of ¼” thick, to make the pressure. The stainless steel cell, with 67 mL capacity, supports 500 bar. In the caps, the cell has Teflon® bronze O-rings which support both, the low temperatures and the working pressures. The cell is equipped with a thermocouple T type (HiP, US) and a pressure transducer S10 (Wika, Germany), within an accuracy of ± 0.02 K and 0.1 bar respectively; both sensors are in direct contact with the sample. One valve (V1 in Fig. 1) allows isolating the cell from the hydraulic compressor and, another valve (V2 in Fig. 1), situated above the cell, acts as a purge. To refrigerate the system, the cell is surrounded by a rubber tubing through which passes the coolant from the cooling bath. Pressure and temperature data were monitored and saved using a Labview program designed to read the sensors signals.

Fractional precipitation experiments have been performed decreasing the temperature slowly from room temperature. Raman spectra of the supernatant were taken at several temperatures, including theoretical crystallization temperatures of each mineral phase. At each temperature of analysis, the system was kept isothermal during 24 hours as stabilization time in order to ensure that the measure was made at equilibrium conditions. A kinetic study was carried out in order to select the stabilization time. As an example of this study, in Fig. 2 is shown the variation concentrations of sulfate (SO_4^{2-}) and carbonate (CO_3^{2-}) ions versus time, in the temperature range from 290 K to 278 K, during the fractional precipitation of the alkaline brine at 300 bar. Concentration stabilization at the new temperature of both ions took 10 hours.

Raman spectroscopy has been employed to follow in situ the precipitation processes of the selected brines. Spectra were excited with a Nd:YAG solid state laser operating at 532 nm at 200mW. After passing through a monochromator, the scattered light was detected with a CCD regulated at 203 K for heat-noise reduction. It was employed a diffraction grating with 600 grooves/mm. Since the CCD has 1024x256 pixels and the scattered Raman light is in a range of 325.1 cm^{-1} to 2535.5 cm^{-1} , the pixel resolution of the equipment is $2.16 \text{ cm}^{-1}/\text{pixel}$ (binning factor = 1). Spectral resolution, with a width slit of $50 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$, is better than 10 cm^{-1} . The diffraction grating is set in an automated turret which allows its rotation and the scanning over a large wavelength range.

In order to quantify the concentration variation, previous calibrations with aqueous solutions of each single compound, i.e. magnesium sulfate (MgSO_4), sodium sulfate (Na_2SO_4), sodium carbonate (Na_2CO_3) and sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4), have been made. As the area of the Raman peak is proportional to the concentration, aqueous

solutions of known concentration have been prepared and analyzed. The analysis consisted of normalizing the spectra of the aqueous solutions with the isosbestic point of the water located at 3468 cm^{-1} (Walrafen et al., 1986), once they were taken. Then, the major peak of each compound was fitted to the curve that best matched (Gaussian, Lorentzian or Voigt), to calculate its area. The areas obtained were adjusted to an empirical equation with the known concentrations of the aqueous solutions. These equations have been employed to calculate the corresponding concentrations of the compounds at the supernatant during the fractional precipitations of the brines. Same calibration curves have been employed for experiments at 300 bar since it has been checked the non-variations of the Raman signal of the compounds at this pressure.

The Raman spectra of the aqueous solutions of each compound with the analyzed peaks indicated are shown in Fig. 3. Both, magnesium sulfate (MgSO_4) and sodium sulfate (Na_2SO_4) have the major signal at 983 cm^{-1} which corresponds with the symmetric stretching mode ν_1 of the SO_4^{2-} (Rudolph et al., 2003). This peak has been fitted to a Gaussian curve with a correlation factor up to 0.99. Sodium carbonate (Na_2CO_3) has been studied from the peak at 1063 cm^{-1} , corresponding to the symmetric stretch C-O ν_1 of the CO_3^{2-} (Rudolph et al., 2008). The band profile has been also fitted to a Gaussian curve with a correlation factor up to 0.99. Sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4), in liquid water, acts as a strong acid in its first dissociation, forming bisulfate (HSO_4^-). But it acts as a weak acid to lose the next proton and form sulfate (SO_4^{2-}). HSO_4^- ion peak appears at 1049 cm^{-1} , resulted from the S-O-H symmetric stretching mode of the bisulfate (Sobron et al., 2007). In the spectra of the sulfuric acid aqueous solution (Fig. 3.c) both sulfate ($\sim 983\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and bisulfate ($\sim 1049\text{ cm}^{-1}$) ions contributions are observed. Peaks have been fitted to double-Lorentzian curve with a correlation factor up to 0.97.

3. RESULTS

In order to interpret correctly the changes observed in the ions concentrations along the precipitation of each brine, it has been studied the variation of the Raman peaks of the aqueous solutions of each compound separately with the temperature. In the case of the salts, the ion signals (i.e. SO_4^{2-} and CO_3^{2-}) keep constant even when ice was formed. Different behaviour has the sulfuric acid aqueous solution. In Fig. 4 the cooling runs performed with (a) a MgSO_4 aqueous solution 0.64 m and (b) a H_2SO_4 aqueous solution 2.5 m are shown. In the case of the solution with sulfuric acid, the signal of the bisulfate ion is more intense than the corresponding to the sulfate ion at 298 K. But with the decrease in temperature the ratio between both is reversed. At 258 K peak intensity of sulfate is the highest.

The Raman spectra of the experiment performed at 1 bar of the quaternary acid brine is shown in Fig. 5. As can be seen, during the cooling from 298 K to 258 K, SO_4^{2-} ion decreased in concentration. This is caused by the precipitation of sulfate minerals. HSO_4^- increases its concentration in the last step of the cooling, after the ice precipitation. When the aqueous solution has only sulfuric acid, HSO_4^- concentration decreases with the temperature (Fig. 4). But, when sulfate salts (i.e. MgSO_4 and Na_2SO_4) are also present, and precipitation occurs, HSO_4^- concentration increases. As the HSO_4^- comes from the sulfuric acid dissociation, we can postulate that, when ice is formed, the sulfuric acid is concentrated in the remaining supernatant. In Fig. 6 are shown Raman spectra of the solids obtained: a) Epsomite, (b) Mirabilite and (c) Meridianiite. In order to confirm the solid phases obtained, spectra were compared with spectra shown in the studies of Genceli et al. (2007) and Hamilton and Menzies (2010). To take the spectra, the flask was extracted from the bath in the shortest possible time to

avoid the destabilization of the minerals formed at low temperature; then, spectra were taken from the flask directly and in a short acquisition time. At 300 bar was not possible take the spectra of solid phases since the sapphire window of the high pressure cell is located at the middle (see Fig. 1) and minerals, when it was formed, sank to the bottom of the cell.

All the experimental results have good reproducibility, and their summaries are represented at Figs. 7, 8, 9 and 10. For the non-neutral brines, pH has been calculated and its variation during the evolution of the aqueous solutions is shown.

Fig. 7.a shows the decrease of the SO_4^{2-} ion concentration when the neutral brine ($\text{MgSO}_4\text{-Na}_2\text{SO}_4\text{-H}_2\text{O}$) was cooled. Theoretical phase diagram (Fig. 7.b) of the system performed by Fitch (1970) has been used in order to predict the precipitating minerals. Since the initial % w/w of each salt in the solution has been 35.2 % of MgSO_4 (2.93 molal) and 23.1 % of Na_2SO_4 (1.63 molal), at 300 K, the system was in the stability zone of the epsomite ($\text{MgSO}_4\cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$). The decrease in the sulfate concentration at the supernatant at the beginning was due to the precipitation of the mineral mentioned, forming the first mineral layer. Just below 285 K, an inflection in the curve (see Fig. 7.a) indicates that mirabilite ($\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4\cdot 10 \text{H}_2\text{O}$) started to form. At about 270 K, epsomite, located below the mirabilite layer, may be replaced by meridianiite ($\text{MgSO}_4\cdot 11\text{H}_2\text{O}$). The eutectic point occurred at 267 K. Hogenboom et al. (1995) studied the binary system $\text{MgSO}_4\text{-H}_2\text{O}$ at a pressure up to 4000 bar, at which the freezing-point depression curve increased in its slope. At 300 bar this trend has not been clearly observed (Fig. 7).

Fractional precipitation of the alkaline brine ($\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4\text{-Na}_2\text{CO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}$) at both 1 and 300 bar is obvious in Fig. 8.a. In this case the phase diagram of Vard and Villiam-Jones (1993) has been employed to know what minerals have been crystallized along

the cooling. The decreased in the CO_3^{2-} ion from 300 K was due to the crystallization of natron ($\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$). From 290 K the drop of the SO_4^{2-} ion concentration indicates the stabilization of mirabilite. Ice started to form at 270 K and the eutectic occurred about 262 K, with the co-existence of the two minerals mentioned with ice. The pH was calculated from the concentration of hydroxyl ions (OH^-), resulted from the CO_3^{2-} hydrolysis (Fig. 8.b). It was decreasing along the cooling due to the precipitation of the carbonate minerals. Estimation of the pH for experiments at 300 bar was made in the same form as for 1 bar, since the effect of pressure hardly varies activity coefficients values (Krumgalz et al., 1999; Samaranayake and Sastry, 2010).

Fig. 9.a shows the precipitation of the sulfate minerals and the subsequent concentration of the sulfuric acid at the supernatant of the ternary acid brine ($\text{MgSO}_4\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4\text{-H}_2\text{O}$), at 1 and 300 bar. Theoretical simulation performed by Marion (2002), at 1 bar, has been used to estimate what minerals were crystallized. The decrease in the SO_4^{2-} ion concentration from the starting of the cooling was obvious (Fig. 9.a). Epsomite was crystallizing from the beginning temperature to 271 K, when it was replaced by meridianiite. Ice was co-formed at 264 K at 1 bar and 268 K at 300 bar. It was observed a rise in the HSO_4^- ion concentration when ice was precipitated. pH of the brine, calculated from the HSO_4^- ion concentration, as a function of the temperature is in Fig. 9.b. At the beginning the HSO_4^- concentration remained almost constant. It caused a decrease after the transformation of the epsomite to meridianiite; it may be caused by the participation of the HSO_4^- ion in the reaction. After the formation of ice, the pH of the supernatant decreases drastically since it was composed by a sulfuric acid-rich solution.

In Fig. 10.a, the quaternary acid brine ($\text{MgSO}_4\text{-Na}_2\text{SO}_4\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4\text{-H}_2\text{O}$) can be observed with the same behavior as the ternary acid brine (Fig. 9.a). To know what

minerals were formed, theoretical simulation of Marion (2002) for the same system has been used. Results obtained at 1 bar and at 300 bar are in agreement with the model. The gradual crystallization of epsomite (300 K), mirabilite (285 K) and meridianiite (271 K) caused the drop in the SO_4^{2-} ion concentration in the supernatant. After ice precipitation, HSO_4^- ion was concentrated in the supernatant and an increase in its concentration was obvious. Fig. 10.b shows the pH values obtained during the cooling. The only difference in the quaternary system respect to the ternary system was no rise in the pH value before the ice formation. In this case a mirabilite layer, formed after the precipitation of epsomite, avoids the interaction between the HSO_4^- ion with the epsomite. Transformation of epsomite into meridianiite may take place, but without the participation of the bisulfate ion such as seen occur on the previous case.

Eutectic temperature of both acid brines was not measured since the amount of supernatant was not sufficient.

The evolution of the sulfate minerals and ice is not affected by the presence of sulfuric acid since the crystallization temperatures and the concentrations at which the species precipitated were similar in both neutral and acid systems.

4. DISCUSSION

In this work, low pH and neutral conditions have been reproduced. The evolution of the pH is opposite comparing both extreme systems. In the alkaline brine, lower temperatures promote the decreases of pH to values around 9, due to the precipitation of carbonate minerals (Fig. 8). On the other hand, the evolution of the acid brines, before it get the eutectic, ends in a solution composed mostly by sulfuric acid,

but not entirely, and therefore the pH is around 0 (Figs. 9 and 10). However, moderate pH values may exist for these non-neutral aqueous cryomagmas if they were less saturated due to several circumstances such as: a diluted concentration of the cryomagmas in origin; the mixture of two or more cryomagmas with different chemical composition in the crust; or the assimilation of part of the icy crust by the cryomagma.

Different initial saturation of the cryomagmas would also modify the fractional precipitation evolution. For example, in the case of the neutral solution in the ternary system, epsomite does not crystallize at magnesium sulfate concentration below 16 % w/w (1.33 molal) until the eutectic temperature of the system (268.2 K) (Fitch, 1970); or in the alkaline case, if the concentration of carbonate at the solution is lower than 26.5 % w/w (2.5 molal) the first mineral stabilized would be nahcolite instead of natron (Vard and William-Jones, 1993).

The decrease in temperature, due to the evolution of the brine rising to the surface or the contact with the cooler icy crust, may cause crystal fractionation, as occur in silicate systems of the Earth's crust. The chemical composition of a cryomagma can also suffer changes for other processes such as assimilation of the crust and/or mixing process with other cryomagmas. As a consequence of these processes several suites of low-temperature mineral assemblages (rocks made by hydrates and ices) appear at the crust (Fig. 11). The most frequent tectonic process that occurs in the crust of Europa is fracturation. During faulting, fast decompression and cooling of the cryomagma with composition A may be produced (see Fig. 11). If solidus temperature is reached rapidly, the cryomagma would be flash frozen and, the composition of the final mineral assemblage at the surface would be the same than of the original brine (FMA 1). If the cryomagma rises to the surface slowly enough to be differentiated due to the temperature decrease, the final mineral assemblage at the surface could be depleted in

some phases by the fractionation of the brine (FMA 2). On the other hand, the crystallization process of the cryomagma may also occur because the chamber walls are cooler than the fluid. Then, the cryomagma, with composition B, would then crystallize from the walls inward; the subsequent layers including several mineral assemblages (MA 1, 2, 3) are formed depending on the composition of the brine as it was demonstrated in these experiments. If the temperature of the brine is sufficient to partially melt the icy crust, the fluid within chamber C may be contaminated by material assimilation. Additionally, the fluid C may mix with other D, changing the composition of the brine to E, resulting in a different complex mineral suite after evolving. The final stage and location of these suites will depend on the local tectonic/thermal regime and the subsequent exogenous alteration. These experiments help to show the possible intricate Europa cryopetrology.

5. CONCLUSIONS

If the non- water ice minerals observed at the surface are endogenous, they will be the product of the evolution of the cryomagmas, and then would be an open window to characterize the potential habitable environments of Europa from the surface. At depth, aqueous environments acquire the acidity and other environmental attributes; then, life, if exists, will be intrinsically linked to the cryomagmatic processes. If the suites of low temperature mineral assemblages are determined with more detail in future space missions, the properties of the cryomagma from which they have been formed could be indirectly approached. One example is the pH of the aqueous solutions, which extremes have been simulated in our experiments and would be expressed at the surface

by a specific mineral assemblage index. In the alkaline solution studied here, pH was calculated just before getting the eutectic, obtaining 9.46 and 10.00 at 1 bar and 300 bar respectively, in agreement with theoretical model done by Marion (2001). For the acid solutions, a drop in pH values in the range 1-0 was observed caused by the increase in sulfuric acid concentration between the two last temperatures of the cooling, when ice started to form (Marion, 2002). In this study biological activity was not taken into account. If life exists in Europa, it may moderate the pH of the environment due to the consumption of part of the oxidants, as Pasek and Greenberg (2012) postulated.

Raman spectroscopy is a useful technique to characterize cryomagmatic brines with different chemical composition and measure their evolution level. This analysis technique is strongly suggested for the future in situ planetary missions when aqueous solutions from melted ice or cryomagmas will be available.

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FIGURE LEGENDS

FIG.1. Sketch of the high pressure cell, coupled to a hydraulic compressor.

FIG.2. Concentrations of sulfate and carbonate ions versus time in a temperature drop step of the alkaline brine from 290 K to 278 K at 300 bar.

FIG.3. Raman spectra of the aqueous solutions of the single compounds that are used to make the calibrations: **(a)** Magnesium sulfate (MgSO_4) and sodium sulfate (Na_2SO_4), **(b)** Sodium carbonate (Na_2CO_3), **(c)** Sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4). The indicated peaks correspond with the major Raman signal of each one, used to perform the analysis.

FIG.4. Comparison of the Raman spectra of aqueous solutions of (a) MgSO_4 and (b) H_2SO_4 at several temperatures. In the first case (a), SO_4^{2-} peak does not varies with the temperature drop; but, in the second case (b), SO_4^{2-} peak increase while HSO_4^- peak decreases with temperature declines.

FIG.5. Raman spectra of the supernatant of the quaternary acid brine taken during the fractional precipitation. Peaks at 983 cm^{-1} and at 1049 cm^{-1} corresponds with sulfate and bisulfate ion signals respectively. Water interactions are appreciable in the O-H symmetric stretching mode ($3200\text{-}4000\text{ cm}^{-1}$). Spectra have been normalized since the isosbestic point of the water (3468 cm^{-1}).

FIG.6. Raman spectra of the minerals obtained in the fractional precipitation of the quaternary acid brine; **(a)** epsomite ($\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$), **(b)** mirabilite ($\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and **(c)** meridianiite ($\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 11\text{H}_2\text{O}$).

FIG.7. (a) Sulfate concentration versus temperature of the experiments at 1 and 300 bar for the neutral brine; MS7: epsomite ($\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$), NaS10: mirabilite ($\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$), MS11: meridianiite ($\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 11\text{H}_2\text{O}$). **(b)** Theoretical phase diagram modified from Fitch (1970).

FIG.8. (a) Variation of the concentration of carbonate and sulfate versus temperature in the experiments at 1 and 300 bar for the alkaline brine; NaC10: natron ($\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$), NaS10: mirabilite ($\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$). **(b)** Decrease of pH during the cooling of the alkaline brine at 1 bar and 300 bar due to the carbonates precipitation.

FIG.9. (a) Variation of the concentration of sulfate and bisulfate versus temperature in the experiments at 1 and 300 bar for the ternary acid brine; MS7: epsomite ($\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$), MS11: meridianiite ($\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 11\text{H}_2\text{O}$). **(b)** pH values for the ternary acid brine at 1 and 300 bar.

FIG.10. (a) Variation of the concentration of sulfate and bisulfate versus temperature in the experiments at 1 and 300 bar for the quaternary acid brine; MS7: epsomite ($\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$), NaS10: mirabilite ($\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$), MS11: meridianiite ($\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 11\text{H}_2\text{O}$). **(b)** pH values for the quaternary acid brine at 1 bar and 300 bar.

FIG.11. Igneous processes that may produce varied cryopetrology in Europa satellite. The cryomagma may suffer flash freezing (by fast cooling), crystal fractionation (by slow cooling), contamination with the icy crust due to temperature differences and/or mixing processes with other cryomagmas (see the text for a detailed discussion).